

Democratising Fab Labs with Open Source Machine Tools

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Abstract

So-called digital fabrication laboratories (commonly referred to as fab labs) have recently challenged the dominant position of large-scale industrial manufacturing by revolutionising the ways in which people approach and interact with production. Fab labs are communal spaces and function as enablers for personal manufacturing. However, while the number of fab labs has surged in recent years, they are primarily concentrated in countries of the global north. This is in parts due to the high cost of machines necessary to set up fab labs and due to the difficult and expensive import and shipping. Repairs and maintenance of these machines often further complicates the matter. Consequently, the setting up of fab labs is often an unachievable endeavour in developing countries.

To facilitate the establishment of fabrication spaces after the fab lab model in developing countries and to mitigate the divide in machine tool access, the concept of Open Source Machine Tools (OSMT) offers a promising solution. The costs associated with the creation of maker spaces based on open source principles are lower compared to traditional fab labs because the machine tools used in them can be manufactured and replicated locally.

Such an approach would also be consistent with the goals and mission of the fab lab movement, which include bridging the digital divide and providing equitable access to knowledge and tools for fabrication. This paper provides a small-scale feasibility study of the incorporation of OSMT into the fab lab framework. Through qualitative interviews with fab lab managers in Tunisia and Germany, the strengths, weaknesses, and potentials of OSMT in the context of personal digital fabrication are examined. Based on this, recommendations are made on how to leverage OSMT for a further democratisation of fab labs in developing countries.

Keywords

Open Source Machine Tools, fab labs

1 Introduction

So-called fabrication laboratories, commonly known as fab labs, have in the last years challenged the dominant position of large-scale industrial manufacturing by making the means of production accessible to individuals. Equipped with an array of digital fabrication machines, they are communal spaces and function as enablers for personal manufacturing. However, this potential for grassroots emancipation is spatially limited and there is a great imbalance in the number of fab labs in countries of the global north and the global south. In developing countries, especially on the African continent, only few fab labs have been set up.

Through a small-scale, qualitative study among lab founders from Germany and Tunisia, the reasons for this gap in fab lab distributions are examined. It is assumed that fab labs in Tunisia face more challenges associated with the procurement of proprietary machine tools, and thus with the very equipment that is essential to set up a fab lab. It is further assumed that Open Source Machine Tools (OSMT) could alleviate this problem by democratising the access to machine tools and drastically reducing their costs. Based on the findings from the study, some recommendations are made regarding whether OSMT should be adopted into the global fab lab movement.

2 Fab labs: Enablers of grassroots technology emancipation?

Originating in the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in 2002, fab labs are communal manufacturing spaces that make digital fabrication tools publicly accessible. Their inventory typically consists of a variety of compatible machines such as 3D printers, laser cutters and milling machines. By allowing anyone to make almost anything through new modes of production, fab labs have even been lauded as the onset of the next industrial revolution [1]. However, while their overall number has surged in recent years, more fab labs have been set up in the global north than the global south. Especially Europe boasts a great number of fab labs while they are comparatively sparse on the African continent. For example, Germany has 70 officially registered fab labs while there are only six labs in Tunisia [2]. This is due to a number of reasons. On the one hand, the proprietary machine tools commonly found on the inventory list of a typical fab lab are almost exclusively produced in industrialised countries [3]. Acquiring these machines is therefore expensive not only due to the lower average purchasing power of developing countries in comparison to the high cost of machines (typically well over USD 100,000 in total for a typical fab lab inventory [4]), but customs tariffs and shipping costs create an additional financial burden. Administrative hurdles and complex bureaucracy can further hinder the process. Moreover, the use and maintenance of imported machine tools can prove difficult when repairs are needed, or spare parts are not available. The setting up of fab labs is therefore often an unachievable endeavour in developing countries. Consequently, the low-threshold technology access provided by fab labs is less available to people living in countries of the global south. This exacerbates the existing socio-economic discrepancy between global north and south in general and the global digital divide in particular: In developing African countries, a persistent lack of technical know-how, digital literacy, and modern manufacturing options remains.

3 Open Source Machine Tools for equitable fab labs

Open source principles are nowadays applied to many different kinds of tangible artifacts. The design files required to replicate them are thereby freely accessible and allow anyone to use, modify, distribute, or sell them [5,6]. Open source machine tools (OSMT), a subcategory of open source hardware (OSH), have been identified as important enabling technological advancements to democratise manufacturing and to mitigate the inequalities in machine tool access [7].

Efforts such as the Open Lab Starter Kit (OLSK) and Machines that Make make use of this to try to democratise the setting up of laboratories and maker spaces by making use of OSMT instead of proprietary machine tools [8,9]. The costs and thresholds associated with the creation of these so-called open labs based on open source principles are lower compared to traditional fab labs because the machine tools used in them can be manufactured and replicated locally, using local resources [10,11]. In this, they are better adaptable to specific spatial and budget constraints and needs, and they enable users to make repairs or replace broken parts compared to commercial machines.

Due to these advantages, it is assumed that the application of OSMT in the fab lab model could facilitate the establishment of fabrication spaces in developing countries. By mitigating the presumed challenges associated with proprietary machine tools, the adoption of OSMT into the fab lab concept potentially

makes the setting up of fab labs cheaper and less riddled by administrative, bureaucratic, and financial hurdles.

4 Integrating Open Source Machine Tools in the fab lab movement

4.1 Data collection

To answer the research hypotheses, qualitative in-depth interviews were conducted with six founders of fab labs and maker spaces in Tunisia and Germany. The labs were randomly selected from all fab labs and maker spaces in the cities Tunis and Hamburg, respective hotspots of the maker scene in Tunisia and Germany [12]. The decision to interview the labs' founders as opposed to other stakeholders such as members or managers was consciously made to ensure that interviewees were aware of both the current processes in the labs as well as challenges during the labs' foundation periods.

To harmonise the process, all six interviews were conducted online and recorded with the interviewees' permission. The recordings were then transcribed and, in several rounds, evaluated by two independent coders. The process and the comprehensive system of deductive and inductive codes developed for it were based on the principles of qualitative content analysis [13,14]. Based on this, the following results were derived.

4.2 Results

As the purpose of their labs, interviewees mentioned education, community-building, and, most importantly, innovation. All three Tunisian labs relied on public funding from associated universities and from EU projects as well as on donations from industry, the German labs also relied on public and private funding from German institutions. Of the labs chosen for the interviews, all possessed commercial machine tools, and one German one additionally relied on machine donations from members. Two of the German labs and two of the Tunisian ones also had self-built machine tools, either bought or built by members. The German lab founders appreciated OSMT for its sustainability and because it was perceived to be bureaucratically less complicated compared to the processes involved with applying for funding to purchase commercial machine tools. Both also mentioned the creative freedom of OSMT and both German and Tunisian labs liked it for the adaptability. Interviewees also valued the personal fulfilment and fun OSMT was perceived to provide to practitioners. The most important point that all interviewees repeatedly stressed was the knowledge of machines that OSMT practitioners gained from building, including the ability to maintain and repair the machines. Challenges related to OSMT as identified by interviewees included difficulties in replicability due to faulty or insufficient documentation and the need to make modifications due to the local unavailability of parts in both Germany and Tunisia. One Tunisian lab founder furthermore mentioned that repair and maintenance of OSMT was challenging. One German interviewee stated that OSMT was not an economically sensible solution when accounting for the time that would be lost for building a machine. However, all interviewees agreed that an OSMT was considerably cheaper compared to a commercial machine and that OSMT gave leeway to try out different things without much financial pressure.

Opposed to this, proprietary machine tools were regarded by one Tunisian interviewee as of more reliable quality, even though the same interviewee apart from that voiced a preference for OSMT. Two other Tunisian lab founders mentioned the advantages of commercial machine tools having a warranty and customer service and being ready to use right upon arrival. Two German interviewees, however, said that they had communication and warranty difficulties with sellers, and one even got cheated by a manufacturer. Two German and two Tunisian labs found commercial machine tools difficult to repair and often had to hire externals for repair and maintenance. Only one Tunisian interviewee stated that they did not have issues with procuring smaller proprietary machine tools because they could be bought from local re-sellers. All other interviewees mentioned difficulties with import and shipping such as high shipping costs, difficult bureaucracy, and customs taxes. Further difficulties recently arose due to external

disruptions such as war and the pandemic disrupting supply chains. Some machines were not at all available to purchase in Tunisia. A point upon which all interviewees agreed was the high price of commercial machine tools and the associated pressure to amortise machine tool purchases.

When asked whether in the future they would prefer to use OSMT or commercial machine tools in their labs, all interviewees agreed that they would at least like to build some more machines in the labs. As reasons for this, they mentioned financial considerations and the creative freedom associated with OSMT and one Tunisian interviewee stated that OSMT creates more dynamic in the fab lab due to more active member participation; one German founder also agreed with that and added that the building of OSMT would equip practitioners with additional skills. Another German interviewee said that OSMT was actually highly suitable for the context of a fab lab as they are not meant to provide spaces for serial production but rather for prototyping and innovation. One Tunisian interviewee stated that using commercial machine tools to replicate OSMT was preferable to build with the desired accuracy. Ultimately, the decision of whether to buy a machine tool or build it would depend on the use purpose and on economic efficiency, according to one German interviewee.

As requirements for the replication of OSMT designs, interviewees mentioned previous experience and knowledge in the domain of engineering to be favourable but not a necessity. Interviewees from both Germany and Tunisia agreed that OSMT practitioners needed a certain passion, the openness to learn-by-doing, and determination and they stressed the need for OSMT designs to be locally adaptable and for machine designers to create comprehensive documentation. The most important point repeatedly mentioned by all interviewees was the need to have a community, both online and in real life, to overcome difficulties in building process and successfully realise an OSMT project.

4.3 Discussion

Albeit a small-scale study with limited scope, the results from the interviews suggest that fab labs in both Tunisia and Germany struggle with challenges that are connected to the commercial machine tools in their inventories. These range from problems with the suppliers over shipping to repair and maintenance. The high purchasing prices of these machines are, however, the biggest challenge that labs face. While the labs can, to a certain degree, decide about which machines they want to buy and which they will forego, they need to possess a certain range of machines to be admitted into the fab lab network. While smaller machines like 3D printers are locally available, more complex and larger machines like laser cutters and large format routers need to be imported; this is especially the case for the Tunisian labs. The purchasing costs for the fab lab inventory typically amount to approximately USD 100,000 [4]. Surprisingly, both German and Tunisian interviewees lamented the high prices of machinery whereas it had been expected to be a more pressing problem for the Tunisian labs. Labs in both Germany and Tunisia relied heavily on public and private funding to buy machines; however, Tunisian labs depended to a large extent on funds allocated to them from EU projects while German labs primarily received finances from the German government and from private companies. The fact that labs in both countries equally struggled with machine procurement shows that the recommended fab lab inventory is too expensive and therefore not inclusive. This might explain why only a handful of fab labs have been set up in Tunisia [2].

The positive attitude of interviewees towards OSMT and the fact that some labs made active use of self-built machines in their everyday activities suggests that the inclusion of OSMT in the list of recommended fab lab inventory is desirable. It could also be an option to give aspiring fab labs the option to opt for OSMT instead of commercial machine tools and make a conscious decision based on available financial and other resources and preferences. Recently, the Fabulaser Mini assembly kit has been adopted into the list of recommended lab inventory by The Fab Foundation [15]. However, this is only a single machine and falls way behind the potential that a wider-reaching inclusion of OSMT could have. While it is an aim of the global fab lab movement that existing labs can produce the equipment for new labs [8], this is not yet a reality. Such a development would make the establishment of fab labs less expensive and more inclusive and would allow for an even swifter and more equitable spread of fab labs. This approach could

even advance the very mission of the global fab lab movement which aims to provide the means “to allow anyone anywhere to make (almost) anything” [4]. By making it considerably cheaper to set up fab labs, the geographic distribution of labs around the globe could be made more equitable and a contribution could be made to bridge the gap in the number of lab labs between countries of the global north and the global south.

However, a wider-reaching inclusion of OSMT into the fab lab context would need to account for certain challenges as well. While it could help to democratise the access to and the establishment of fab labs, OSMT cannot be regarded as a singular solution to this problem. The fact that fab labs in both Germany and Tunisia struggle with funds shows that financial aspects are not the sole barriers to the setting up of larger numbers of fab labs in the global south and that this gap could therefore not be resolved only by the inclusion of OSMT. Further challenges need to be identified and solutions need to be tailored for them. Furthermore, any manufacturing space or fab lab that hopes to, partially or fully, replace proprietary machine tools needs to account for the challenges associated with OSMT. While OSMT provide a low-threshold opportunity to get access to machine tools, this can also be a danger when either the building process or the finished machine pose safety issues to practitioners and users. Only users with a certain degree of engineering domain knowledge should therefore build or make modifications to the machines. Most OSMT projects do not undergo a formalised safety and quality assessment before they are made available online, and practitioners with little to no previous machine building experience are likely prone to errors while building. While in a private context, such dangers are at the risk of the individual, fab labs as public spaces require high-quality, reliable, and, most importantly, safe machines. To mitigate the dangers that faulty or dilettantish machine tools could pose to fab lab users, it is necessary to include safety checks and certification procedures for OSMT projects that are intended to become fab lab inventory. OSMT designs that are being considered for building need to be thoroughly examined before the start of building, and the finished product needs to be evaluated by experts as well before it is made accessible to other fab lab members. Replication of OSMT projects can also be hindered by missing or false information in the build instructions, making extensive trouble-shooting necessary and prolonging the building process. Apart from that, it is important to choose OSMT designs that allow for modifications for the setting up of fab labs. Many OSMT projects are developed in countries of the global north, and some components might be locally unavailable and require alternative solutions due to the high regional differences in the of parts and resources [7]. OSMT projects therefore need to be chosen that allow users to adapt the machine to local contexts and cater to the specific needs and conditions of the respective fab lab.

5 Conclusion

Different to the initial hypothesis, fab labs in Tunisia and Germany faced similar challenges. Those were primarily related to funding and to difficulties in the procurement of proprietary machine tools. However, while the labs in Hamburg primarily accessed funds from Germany of different kinds, the Tunisian labs were reliant on EU aid, and thus, on foreign funds. Ultimately, the underlying reasons for the gap in fab lab distribution of the two cities could not be established without some remaining doubt. However, it has been shown that OSMT nonetheless constitutes a promising development opportunity for the fab lab movement. Many labs already produce and use self-built machine tools and appreciate them for being less costly, more unbureaucratic, and of more educational value than commercial machines. While it is vital to implement measures for quality control and safeguarding, OSMT have the potential to advance the fab lab mission of making the means of production accessible to anyone anywhere.

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